

Education Reforms Outline

教育改革纲要（1978年）

Introduction

Education is an important part of the superstructure of society and plays an important role in the development of the socialist cause. The current education system must be reformed to meet the needs of the new era.

I. Aims of Education

To train builders and successors of socialism who have a firm proletarian world outlook, a high level of culture, and a good command of modern science and technology.

To promote the unity and solidarity of the working class, the peasantry, and the intelligentsia.

To promote the development of socialist culture.

II. Guiding Ideology

The guiding ideology of education is Marxism-Leninism, Mao Zedong Thought, and Deng Xiaoping Theory.

The Party's basic line is the fundamental principle for educational work.

III. Education System

The education system should combine general education with specialized education, and combine knowledge with practice.

The education system should be reformed to meet the needs of the new era, and the development of different types of education should be promoted.

IV. Educational Content

The educational content should be comprehensive, and should include scientific, cultural, and ideological education.

The educational content should be reformed to meet the needs of the new era.

V. V. Teaching Methods

The teaching methods should combine theory with practice, and combine moral education with intellectual education.

The teaching methods should be reformed to meet the needs of the new era.

VI. VI. Teachers

Teachers should be revolutionaries who have a firm proletarian world outlook, a high level of culture, and a good command of modern science and technology.

Teachers should be trained to meet the needs of the new era.

VII. VII. Students

Students should come from among the workers, peasants, and soldiers, and should be educated to have a firm proletarian world outlook, a high level of culture, and a good command of modern science and technology.

The development of different types of education should be promoted to meet the needs of the new era.

VIII. VIII. Educational Institutions

The management of educational institutions should be improved, and democratic management should be promoted.

The establishment of different types of educational institutions should be promoted to meet the needs of the new era.

IX. IX. Educational Funds

The state should provide adequate funding for education.

Social organizations and individuals should be encouraged to participate in the development of education.

X. X. Educational Research

Educational research should be strengthened.

The development of different types of educational research should be promoted to meet the needs of the new era.

XI. XI. International Exchanges and Cooperation

International exchanges and cooperation in education should be promoted.

The development of different types of international exchanges and cooperation in education should be promoted to meet the needs of the new era."

Source: https://www.chinaeducenter.com/en/cedu/edu_system/1978_reform.shtml